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Abstract:

Many people don't understand the DNA of the Toyota Production System and the core values of the Toyota Way. I have seen many who think about the TPS as a tool kit or lean manufacturing techniques that only work with Toyota because Toyota has a different process, a stable environment, or less fluctuation in customer demand. Others believe the TPS works only in the automotive industry.

Jeff K. Liker came out with a remarkable series of books starting with *The Toyota Way* (2003) and ending with *The Toyota Way to Lean Leadership* (Liker and Convis 2012). He revealed the real TPS based on his thirty-plus years of experience studying Toyota. It took him seven books to explain and decode the TPS. It is a Thinking Production System. It is neither a waste removal tool nor a lean manufacturing tactic. Liker presented very well the leadership model behind the system's success.

The TPS is really not what many think. So, what is TPS?

TPS Is a Thinking Production System

The real point is to make people think and people are the value of the system. One of the students of Taiichi Ohno said "We at Toyota made a mistake. We should have never called it the Toyota

Production System, we should have called it the Thinking Production System. Because the real point is to make people think and people are the value of the system." The TPS is made by people, adapted by people, improved by people, and is being improved by people every day and every year. Toyota's employees are making several improvements to the process every day and thousands of improvements every year.

When a company say TPS didn't work for us, it is a leadership failure. They have tried to use the tools in a rigid way. The tools are flexible, adaptable, and implementable in many different conditions and industries. That's why you have to think about the tools and use your own mind. Develop your people and motivate them to think and act.

TPS Is a Long-Term Innovation Process

Without innovation, Toyota would have never have succeeded in anything. Toyota's R&D department has played a major role in Toyota's success. For example, the Toyota wiring loom has gone through several major improvements and developments. The Toyota Prius was the first hybrid vehicle. *Minomi* is a revolution in the material movement. For those who don't know minomi, it is an innovation initiated in Japan. It is focused on eliminating containers completely. One of the Toyota companies in Japan (Central Motors) successfully created a revolution in material flow through a well-designed system to move parts without containers. The system is called minomi. The details are in *The Toyota Way to Lean Leadership* by Liker and Convis (2012).

TPS Is a Customizable Production System

The system can't be copied. What has worked in one environment or specific industry may not work in the other. Even from one Toyota plant to another, the system can't be copied identically. You have to think and adapt the tools. You must tailor them to your needs to suit the current conditions. The best example comes from the minomi system. When the Toyota plant in Georgetown, Kentucky, tried to copy and paste the technique from the Japanese plant, the

process failed. Later, Gary Convis, the president of the Kentucky plant, led the implementation of the new method using the Toyota Way. They had success because Gary was trained very well in lean thinking. This leads again to the first point. The TPS is a Thinking Production System. The real point is to make people think, and the system won't succeed without leaders trained on lean thinking and lean culture.

TPS Is a Productivity Improvement System

The TPS is not only for manufacturing. The TPS gives outstanding results in any area in which you want to achieve overall improvement in productivity, quality, safety, and reliability. It works very well with many different industries and businesses, and that includes health care, hotels, banking, construction, and more. The problem with the word "production" is that it makes many people think the system is for manufacturing. What about accelerating the check-in and check-out processes in a hotel? Won't this improve productivity and customer experience? There are many success stories outside of manufacturing industries presented in various lean references. However, people somehow managed to ignore the whole-system aspect of lean thinking and started calling it "lean" or "lean manufacturing" instead. This reduction in scope allowed business leaders to dismiss lean as a manufacturing idea. As a result, manufacturing companies believed that lean could be delegated, and non-manufacturing companies believed that lean didn't apply to them at all.

TPS Is the Toyota Problem-Solving Routine

Toyota has its own unique way in solving problems and developing leaders. Toyota has a psychology of process improvement unlike its other competitor. Toyota Kata was introduced by Mike Rother to address the needs for improvement. Kata is a Japanese term and is used in many Japanese martial arts. Literately mean "way of doing" and refers to a series of practice moves to build on form and technique. As Rother (2009) presented what is the core form and technique that we want to build in leaders? 1. The ability to systematically improve processes toward a clear target (Improvement Kata) 2. The ability to coach others on the Improvement Kata

(Coaching Kata). The routine of process improvement is done through the Toyota improvement kata, and the routine of coaching people is done through the Toyota coaching kata. The Deming cycle (PDCA) is a learning cycle rather than a process improvement cycle. If you have solved the problem and didn't develop your people, then the process will fail! People won't be able to continue managing the process with the new way if they haven't been trained on the culture of continuous improvement. Things will slip back and it will be difficult to sustain the lean results which is the problem in many companies. I highly encourage you to read the article *A New Routine for Culture Change* by Soliman (2015).

TPS Is Toyota's People and Systems

People built, modified, and improved this system. People are the foundation of continuous improvement. People are more important than the process, and companies should give higher priority to developing their people and providing excellent working environments for them. Unfortunately, many companies say they do lean, Six Sigma, and other improvement projects to boost morale and develop new routines of thinking. However, they are actually focusing only on the processes and seeking quick outcomes. Toyota is highly committed to leadership development and training and coaching their employees. In *Toyota Under Fire* by Liker and Ogden (2010), when Liker interviewed Akio Toyoda after several recall crises, Mr. Toyoda said the rate of growth had been higher than the rate of people development.

TPS Is a System to Build Quality for Customers

Jidoka is one of the main pillars of the TPS. The TPS is represented like a roof. Take away any of the pillars holding up the roof, and the system will collapse. Take out quality, and there is no TPS. Jidoka is a principle of building quality for customers—not inspecting quality. Building quality mean making it right the first time. If you are making defective products or using unacceptable quality standards and filtering these defects out through an inspection system, there is no building quality—and no jidoka. You are just catching the mistakes made in the manufacturing process. This costs a lot of money and resources and puts the business at risk if a defective product passes to the customer. Quality is what keeps any organization in business.

TPS Is a Strategy

The TPS is a strategy for excellence. The TPS is a strategy to achieve the goals of excellence in quality, productivity, costs, safety, and morale (Liker and Trachilis 2015). Without a vision aligned with the strategic objectives and stretch goals, the improvement effort will have no direction. The hoshin kanri process will help align the goals, plans, and efforts toward a common goal in order to achieve strategic business objectives. Hoshin kanri pays attention to the method rather than the results—unlike other traditional management approaches, such as MBO. Hoshin kanri focuses on the innovative methods of achieving the target under a high motivation and development system.

TPS Is Total Performance Solutions

If used properly, these tools can turn around any organization. Speed kills competition. All the tools you need to maximize your productivity, quality, speed, and deliveries are included in the TPS. You just need to learn how to use these tools and implement the culture required to use them in your organization. Remember, a good culture will last forever. A good tool kit under a stressed management system will die quickly. It is all about leadership and how you are going to use these tools.

TPS Is Not Lean

Yes, people called it an inventory reduction program when they first heard of it. “Just in time” is one of the main pillars in the TPS. “Just in time” ideally means “one-piece flow.” Inventory is the greatest waste in the process, and it hides many problems, such as quality problems, breakdown times, waiting waste, and more. Let’s get back to history. Prior to the 1970 oil crisis, very few people in the world know what Toyota was up to. The fact that it emerged stronger than ever while many of its competitors were quite battered made people take notice. People went to Japan to find out how Toyota had done this. What people found was that Toyota was doing something called “just in time.” In the West, this was interpreted as an inventory reduction program. As a result, it became known as the “just-in-time inventory” program. Nobody really

believed inventory could be taken out of the whole value stream. Therefore, “just in time” came to mean “go beat the heck out of your suppliers.” The big three auto companies (Ford, General Motors, and Chrysler) had lots of power over their suppliers, and they became pretty expert at this tactic—to their eventual detriment. James P. Womack came forward with *Lean Thinking* in 1996 and helped many to see the whole value chain. He showed how waste clogs the system and how continuous improvement was needed to link all parts of the chain to customer demand. He explained his findings in plain English, but once again people didn’t hear. Lean might be an element of the larger strategy, but it is most likely to be relegated to plant and manufacturing work. As a result, one company after another has tried lean and failed.

TPS Is Not a Translated Production System

Many techniques used today (with awareness or not) have Japanese names. This includes techniques such as *poka yoke*, *hoshin kanri*, *genchi genbutsu*, and others. The TPS is not a documented process. It can, therefore, be translated via people in Japan and the United States and passed through different cultures. Taiichi Ohno refused at the beginning to document the TPS for fear that people would narrowly focus on tools and theories. He said to write it would be to kill it. For example, “genchi genbutsu,” or *gemba*, is translated as “go and see.” Leaders, however, will only go and see when there is a problem. *Gemba* is being used only as a problem-solving process. *Gemba* is a place for teaching and learning management. *Gemba* is the place where value-creating work happens and where you should put value for your customers. All lean tools and techniques, such as value stream mapping, work-standardization processes, and more, must be planned, measured, adapted, standardized, and improved at the workplace. *Gemba* is a place to solve problems by grasping the current situation and finding the root causes of problems by asking the five whys (Ahmed 2014).

TPS Is a Pull System—Not a Kanban System

A pull system is the key to avoiding overproduction waste. You are linking the chain to customer demand instead of a schedule. You are no longer producing based on a schedule. As presented in

The Toyota Way, kanban is an organized system of inventory buffers. According to Ohno, inventory is a waste, so kanban is something to strive to get rid of—not be proud of.

TPS Is Not Making to Order in Sequence

The TPS promotes leveling rather than making to order in sequence. Most suppliers try to follow the lean principle of making to order. However, since customer demands are never stable and are naturally unpredictable, irregular, and significantly varied, following the customer demand in sequence can cause a lot of issues and waste. You have to level the product volume and type. That's why many businesses have difficulties building to order. This is also why they say Toyota has a stable environment and less fluctuation in customer demand and why the TPS is only suitable for Toyota. They don't understand the underlying power of leveling.

TPS Is an Eight-Step Toyota Business Practice

Those are the eight steps of Toyota business practice in solving problems. 1. Define the problem relative to the ideal (plan). 2. Break down the problem into manageable pieces (plan). 3. Find the root cause of the problem (plan). 4. Set the targets for achievement (plan). 5. Select the suitable solution from different countermeasures (plan). 6. Implement the plan (do). 7. Revise the outcomes as expected (check). 8. Find out what is going wrong, adapt, adjust, and then repeat the cycle (act). The plan is invoked 5 times, this is to ensure that the root cause of the problem has been eliminated. Lean emphasizes the plan. The plan phase cannot be created without a daily observation at the gemba to find the root causes of problems, gather facts, discuss things with the process operators, and develop the best countermeasure from different alternatives. For more about how the Deming cycle is utilized to develop leaders, read the article *A New Routine for Culture Change* by (Soliman 2015).

TPS Is Not Zero Inventory

Many think just-in-time inventory means zero inventory. The ideal thing is one-piece flow, and this can only be established through a production cell. There is an inventory buffer, but it is not often used. There is a buffer in the Andon¹ system. There is a buffer to protect your customer. There is a buffer to avoid stopping the whole production line to fix a problem. There is a buffer to avoid breaking down a critical manufacturing process.

TPS Is Built on Deep Supplier Relationships

This is one of the most important factors in Toyota's success. It was explained in chapter 3, which discussed teamwork and Toyota's core values. Few companies realize the importance of working with your suppliers to improve your own process and the value you provide to your customers. If you are not working with your suppliers to truly reduce inventory holdings, the process will fail. If you are trying to reduce inventory and ask your supplier to deliver smaller batch sizes more frequently, and if your supplier is not ready, the process will fail. I have seen many companies trying to shift the costs of holding inventory to their suppliers. This offers no real savings in the complete value stream! You are redistributing the cost to suppliers, but there are no real savings. Very few people understand this. I recommend reading *Building Deep Supplier Relationships* from the Harvard Business Review (Liker and Choi 2004). Building these kinds of relations with suppliers is one of the most difficult parts of implementing the TPS, but it is also the most important part.

This report is not about explaining TPS in a few sentences. As I mentioned, it took Jeff K. Liker seven books to explain the real TPS. The purpose of these short sentences is to serve as a

¹ The Andon system is a part of the Toyota principle of building quality for customers (jidoka) and refers to the use of an alarm system on the production line to prevent defects from passing to the next process.

reminder. They are to provide you with just a specific level of awareness. You have to read more, practice, and perform real projects in order to gather in-depth knowledge.

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